

A Systematic Review: Insights on Understanding and Designing Hepatic Drug Delivery Research

T. Mahesh Kumar*, **G. Dhiya**, **V. Mohana Bharathi**, **U. Malar Mannan** and **P. Ananthi**

Department Of Pharmaceutics, Sankaralingam Bhuvaneshwari College Of Pharmacy (Affiliated To The Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University), Sivakasi - 626130, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Liver is the largest gland and one of the most vital organ in the human body that is responsible for an array of functions that help metabolism, immunity, digestion, detoxification, vitamin storage, excretion of waste metabolites, and the synthesis of various proteins. Its primary function is to control the flow and safety of substances absorbed from the digestive system before it's systemic circulation. The major liver diseases, such as viral hepatitis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma, are significant global health issues that contribute more than 2 million deaths per annum worldwide. Even though various medication and surgical treatment options are available, effective treatment remains a challenge today, because of the drawbacks of the existing drug delivery methods, such as the inability to deliver an adequate concentration of drugs to the diseased liver, non-specific drug distribution, reduction in bioavailability, and negative effects on healthy tissues. Many liver diseases remain incurable, and therefore, currently the liver is an important target for drug delivery research, and the healthcare researcher needs to contribute scientific study outcomes continuously for improving the health of patients suffering from illnesses of liver. For performing hepatic-related research, it is important to have a basic and thorough understanding of liver anatomy, pathophysiological functions, metabolic pathways, types of liver diseases, current treatments, drugs available or approved in the market, new therapeutics under research and advances in drug delivery systems. This review discusses all these aspects of liver related challenges and give directions for future researchers in this domain for patient wellness.

Keywords: liver diseases, pathophysiology, treatment, new therapeutics, advanced drug delivery.

INTRODUCTION

The liver performs hundreds of vital functions and plays a role in nearly every organ system in the body. It interacts with the endocrine and gastrointestinal systems by aiding digestion and metabolism. The liver is the storage location for fat-soluble vitamins and handles cholesterol homeostasis. It plays a role in haematology with clotting factors and protein synthesis. The liver plays a role in heme breakdown into unconjugated bilirubin and conjugates it. It involves a role in sex hormone metabolism and produces carrier proteins that are important in reproduction and development. The kupffer and pit cells play an important role in the body's immunological system.^[1] The liver produces bile to

aid in fat digestion, metabolizes and balances carbohydrates, fats, and proteins.

The disorders of liver functions triggered by various hepatic diseases, including hepatitis B virus infection, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), hepatic fibrosis, hepatocellular carcinoma, and transplant rejection, significantly threaten human health worldwide. The pathophysiology of liver diseases involves initial impacts on the liver followed by further harm, ultimately leading to liver damage and multiple organ failure. Indeed, liver damage and organ failure encompass the harm produced by several substances, including acetaminophen, hepatitis B and C viruses (HBV and HCV), and oxidative stress, resulting in the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines and, ultimately, leading to

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

liver failure. Moreover, these processes can also involve the activation of hepatic stellate cells (HSCs), resulting in the secretion and deposition of extracellular matrix components, leading to liver fibrosis progressing to cirrhosis and ultimately hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). Various pathophysiological mechanisms contribute to the progression of liver diseases are the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), cytokine release, the involvement of hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) in inflammation, and the role of autophagy in hepatocytes, which leads to acute inflammation via damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs).

Clinical treatment methods for hepatic diseases are diverse, including surgical interventions (hepatectomy and liver transplantation), ablation therapy, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, antiviral therapy, and immunotherapy. Although great achievements have been obtained in the clinic, some challenges limit the successful applications of current hepatic disease therapies. For example, incomplete resection may induce tumour recurrence; conventional pharmacotherapy may generate drug resistance, and result in severe systemic toxicity and limited therapeutic efficacy due to their lack of targeting ability; and the patients need to take immunosuppressant drugs for the remainder of their lives to avoid transplant rejection after liver transplantation (LT), which may induce severe side effects and reduce their living quality. Especially, owing to the various and complex etiologies of liver diseases, no standard medication is available for their clinical treatment despite the proven effectiveness of some therapeutic agents in clinical trials. Nevertheless, conventional medications cannot be delivered to the location of diseases at a sufficient concentration and may cause significant adverse effects. In recent years, various polymer-based nanomedicines have been designed and developed to carry small molecules, peptides and nucleic acids for the diagnosis and treatment of hepatic diseases, resulting in improved therapeutic outcomes and alleviated systemic toxicity. Recently, nanomedicines have been reported to have the capacity to improve the therapeutic outcomes and reduce the side effects of medications (e.g., natural extracts, chemotherapeutic drugs and nucleic acid-based drugs) by facilitating liver-specific drug delivery, thus

offering a new paradigm to address the aforementioned challenges.^[2,3] In the last few years, numerous drug delivery approaches for specific targeting of HSCs have been studied, for example, liposomes, protein-based delivery systems, viral vectors, and inorganic delivery systems, which can reduce drug adverse effects and further improve the therapeutic effects of drugs. However, the clinical application of nanomedicines is still limited, and several challenges hinder the clinical translation of nanomedicines that needs to be addressed in the future.

In this present review various aspects necessary to understand before starting of liver related drug delivery research are presented in a streamline fashion which includes: liver anatomy, pathophysiology of liver diseases and hepatic metabolism of drug and other substances; types of common liver diseases and various treatment strategies; targeting of drugs for non-alcoholic fatty liver (NAFL) and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC); emerging therapies like histotripsy, regenerative medicine and cell therapies; novel drug delivery system using lipid based formulations, exosomes, and polymeric/non-lipid nanoparticles; biological carriers of bacterial and viral platforms; advanced techniques of smart and responsive delivery systems of drug targeting, immunotherapy, gene-based drug delivery; targeted drug therapy to liver by active, passive, inverse, ligand based, double, dual, and physical targeting.

ANATOMY OF LIVER

The liver is situated in the upper part of the abdominal cavity under the ribcage on the right-hand side, occupying the greater part of the right hypochondriac region, part of the epigastric region and extending into the left hypochondriac region. Liver comprises around 2-3% of an adult's body weight, ranges between 1200 to 1800 g. The liver is unique due to its dual blood supply from the portal vein (approximately 75%) and the hepatic artery (approximately 25%).^[4,5]

Structurally liver consists of 2 main lobes, both are made up of 8 segments that consist of more than 1000 lobules (small lobes). These lobules are functional and structural units of the liver connected to small ducts (tubes) that connect with larger ducts to form the common hepatic duct. Hepatic lobule measures

approximately 2.0 x 0.7 mm and is composed of hepatocyte plates organized in a solid hexagonal shape surrounding the central vein. It is separated by the anastomosing system of sinusoids that perfuse cells with a mixture of portal and arterial blood. A portal triad containing the hepatic artery, the portal vein, and the bile ducts is arranged around each vertex

of the hepatocyte-formed hexagon. Moreover, the hepatic sinusoid has a diameter of approximately 5 to 10 μm , and could facilitate the exchange of substances between the blood and the perisinusoidal space of Disse. Figure 1 shows the anterior and posterior views of the human liver.

Figure 1: Anatomy of human liver

Liver consists of parenchymal cells and non-parenchymal cells (NPCs). The parenchymal cells include hepatocytes, which account for 70–80% of the cells in the liver and are the principal cell type in the liver. The NPCs mainly include liver sinusoidal endothelial cells (LSECs), kupffer cells (KCs), and hepatic stellate cells (HSCs). LSECs form the lining of the hepatic sinusoid and have fenestra with a pore size of approximately 100–200 nm. KCs account for 80–90% of the total number of macrophages in the body, and are intrinsic parts of the reticuloendothelial system. HSCs make up nearly one-third of the NPCs, reside in the space of Disse, and directly contact LSECs, hepatocytes, and other HSCs.^{6,7}

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY AND ASSESSMENT OF LIVER DISEASES ^[8,9]

The pathophysiology of liver disease centers on a chronic, persistent injury that triggers sustained inflammation, activation of hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) to produce excessive extracellular matrix (ECM), leading to liver fibrosis. Continued injury

results in irreversible fibrosis, distorted liver architecture, regenerative nodule formation, and cirrhosis. This architectural damage, especially in later stages, leads to complications like ascites and hepatic encephalopathy. The core pathophysiological processes are below:

Persistent liver injury: Various etiologies, including viral infections (like hepatitis viruses), toxins, alcohol, metabolic disorders, and autoimmune processes, can cause chronic damage to liver cells (hepatocytes). **Inflammation and fibrosis:** The initial damage triggers an inflammatory response. In response, liver stellate cells are activated to become myofibroblasts, which then produce and accumulate excessive amounts of ECM components, leading to fibrosis (scarring). **Regeneration and nodules:** The liver attempts to repair itself by forming regenerative nodules. However, this process of "wound healing" contributes to the architectural distortion seen in the later stages of disease. **Cirrhosis:** If the underlying injury continues, the reversible fibrotic changes progress to irreversible, advanced fibrosis and nodule formation, culminating in cirrhosis. **Functional and**

structural changes: Cirrhosis leads to a loss of normal liver structure and function. This architectural distortion is the primary driver for many of the complications of advanced liver disease.

The structural changes in the liver increase pressure in the portal vein, leading to portal hypertension. This portal hypertension drives complications such as ascites (fluid build-up in the abdomen), variceal hemorrhage (bleeding from enlarged veins in the esophagus and stomach), hepatic encephalopathy (brain dysfunction due to toxins that the liver can't clear properly), hepatorenal syndrome (kidney failure caused by liver disease), and hepatocellular carcinoma (patients with cirrhosis have an increased risk of developing liver cancer). Liver cirrhosis results from continuous liver injury, inflammation, fibrosis, and necrosis. Alcoholism and chronic hepatitis B and C commonly cause cirrhosis. Hepatitis C is the most damaging. The fibrosis in cirrhosis occurs from the secretion of TGF-beta from the Ito cells in the space of Disse. Cirrhosis usually represents end-stage liver disease, and as such, liver function is greatly compromised. The diminished ability to produce protein and detoxify substances results in symptoms of portal hypertension, hyperestrinism, and hypoalbuminemia. Decreased clotting factor synthesis results in coagulopathy. Its presentation arises from manifestations of diminished hepatic function and portal hypertension.

Jaundice is often a sign of altered bilirubin metabolism. The first sign of jaundice is often yellowing under the tongue, followed by scleral icterus (yellowing of the sclera). There are numerous causes for jaundice, which can typically be classified by getting a fractionated bilirubin where indirect bilirubin (unconjugated bilirubin) and direct bilirubin (conjugated bilirubin) are measured. The result of the fractionated bilirubin can help to identify the etiology of the cholestasis into prehepatic and intrahepatic or extrahepatic causes. A common etiology of prehepatic jaundice is hemolysis, where the level of hemolysis overwhelms the conjugating capacity of the liver, resulting in a buildup of unconjugated bilirubin, causing jaundice. Causes of intrahepatic cholestasis can be congenital diseases, such as Gilbert syndrome and Crigler-Najjar syndrome. In these congenital diseases, the enzyme responsible for bilirubin

conjugation, UDP-glucuronosyltransferase (UGT), is mildly deficient or completely deficient. Dubin-Johnson and Rotor syndrome are causes of direct bilirubinemia, as there is a defect in canalicular transport of conjugated bilirubin. Other causes of post-hepatic cholestasis are an obstruction, such as due to a stone or malignancy. Viral hepatitis can result in both indirect and direct hyperbilirubinemia.

The Child-Pugh score and the model for end-stage liver disease (MELD) score are both used to assess and determine prognosis in patients with cirrhosis. Both look at a combination of variables to score the patient. The Child-Pugh score evaluates ascites, hepatic encephalopathy (HE), total bilirubin, albumin, and prothrombin time or INR (International Normalized Ratio). The MELD score uses creatinine, bilirubin, and INR. While both are used to create a predictive model for cirrhotic patients, the MELD score is the scale of choice for the evaluation of liver transplant patients.

METABOLISM IN THE LIVER

The liver is the main site of drug metabolism. This is primarily a detoxification mechanism whereby the body converts pharmacologically active lipid-soluble drugs into inactive hydrophilic metabolites, which can then be excreted by the kidneys. On occasions, metabolic enzymes are also needed for the conversion of prodrugs to their active components. The metabolism in the liver is important for lipid-soluble drugs, whereas renal excretion is more important for hydrophilic drugs.

Patients with liver disease often require drug treatment, either for their liver disease and its complications or for other common concomitant conditions such as cardiovascular disease. Liver disease has major effects on drug response, which exposes these patients to a higher risk of drug-drug interactions (DDIs). In one survey, 13% of all DDIs led to an adverse drug reaction; most adverse drug reactions occurred in patients with the most severe hepatic impairment. To ensure safe and effective therapy, prescribers should be aware of the way in which drug responses can be affected in patients with liver disease. Drug regulatory agencies such as the US FDA require pharmacokinetic studies to be undertaken in patients with hepatic impairment when

hepatic metabolism accounts for 20% or more of the elimination of a drug under development and/or if the drug has a low therapeutic index. Furthermore, dose reduction is required when there is a ≥ 2 -fold increase in the area under the curve in hepatic impairment. As a general rule, therefore, drugs that undergo hepatic metabolism are more likely to require dosage alteration (of the loading or maintenance dose or both, especially if the therapeutic index is low) in patients with liver impairment than are drugs that predominantly undergo renal excretion, although there are exceptions.

Fat-soluble vitamin storage and metabolism: Most fat-soluble vitamins reach the liver via intestinal absorption in the form of chylomicrons or VLDL. The liver stores and/or metabolizes fat-soluble vitamins. Vitamin A is stored in Ito cells. It can undergo oxidation into retinal, followed by retinoic acid for phototransduction, or retinoic acid can be conjugated into glucuronide for secretion into bile. Whether vitamin D3 comes from the skin, animal products, or plant products, it must undergo 25-hydroxylation by the hepatic CYP-450 system, which is further hydroxylated in the kidney to achieve its functional form. The hepatic CYP-450 system then hydroxylates carbon 24 to render vitamin D inactive. The liver receives vitamin E in its alpha and gamma-tocopherol forms. Alpha-tocopherol is integrated with VLDL or HDL in the liver and is then secreted back into circulation, while the liver metabolizes the gamma-tocopherol form for excretion. While vitamin K is not stored or metabolized in the liver, its presence is essential as the liver enzyme gamma-glutamyl carboxylase requires it for gamma-carboxylation of coagulation factors II, VII, IX, X, protein C and protein S.

Drug metabolism:^[10,11] The critical function of the liver is detoxification of xenobiotics. The liver functions to transform xenobiotics mainly by converting them from a lipophilic form to a hydrophilic form through phase I and phase II. These

reactions mainly take place in the smooth endoplasmic reticulum of hepatocytes. Phase I reactions create a more hydrophilic solute via oxidation, reduction, and hydrolysis using the cytochrome P450 (CYP450) family of enzymes. The product of phase I has an oxygen species that reacts better with enzymes involved with phase II reactions. Phase II reactions conjugate the metabolites created in phase I to make them more hydrophilic for secretion into blood or bile by glucuronate or glutathione, or sulphate conjugation. The phase III pathway is represented by active drug transport processes across cellular membranes rather than enzyme-catalysed reactions; these include both efflux (e.g., P-glycoprotein) and influx (e.g., organic anion transporters) transporters. In phase III, transporters move these metabolites out of the liver cells for elimination. Other organs, such as the kidney and gut, can aid drug metabolism. Multiple factors, such as age, gender, drug-drug interactions, diabetes, pregnancy, liver or kidney disease, inflammation, or genetics, to name a few, affect drug metabolism.^[12,13]

Bilirubin metabolism: The liver plays a significant role in the breakdown of heme. Hemolysis takes place in multiple locations throughout the body, including the liver, spleen, and bone marrow. Heme is broken down into biliverdin, which is then reduced to unconjugated bilirubin. The liver receives unconjugated bilirubin bound to albumin from the circulation. The unconjugated bilirubin then undergoes conjugation via the uridine diphosphate glucuronyl transferase (UGT) system, a phase II process, to become hydrophilic. The newly conjugated bilirubin is then secreted via bile canaliculi into the bile, or small amounts dissolve in the blood, where it then gets filtered for excretion by the kidneys. Most conjugated bilirubin enters the bile and is excreted with bile in feces as it is not absorbable by the intestinal wall. Some bilirubin is converted to urobilinogen or unconjugated bilirubin by gut bacteria for reabsorption to undergo enterohepatic circulation.^[14,15]

MAJOR LIVER DISEASES

Major diseases related to the human liver can be classified by their specific causes or nature or their affected liver component, and shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Classification of Major Liver Diseases

(i) Infectious Liver Diseases

Hepatitis: Hepatitis refers to the inflammation of the liver parenchyma and can occur for a variety of reasons, ranging from a temporary asymptomatic viral disease to chronic liver disease and progressive liver failure. Hepatotropic viruses are the most common causes of hepatitis worldwide; nevertheless, other infectious agents, drugs, toxins, and autoimmune and metabolic diseases can also affect a person with this clinical sign. Other viruses causing hepatitis include Epstein-barr virus (EBV), Chickenpox (VZV), Herpes virus (HSV), and Cytomegalovirus (CMV), which are non-hepatotropic viruses infecting the liver as a part of a systemic infection. The viruses are the causes of five main types of hepatitis A, B, C, D, and E. About 400 million people worldwide are chronic carriers of the hepatitis virus.^[16]

Hepatitis A: Hepatitis A is a viral liver disease that can cause mild to severe illness. The hepatitis A virus is primarily transmitted by the faecal-oral route, when an uninfected person ingests food or water that has been contaminated with the faeces of an infected

person. Anyone who has not been vaccinated or previously infected can get infected with the hepatitis A virus. Hepatitis A infections occur due to risk factors that include poor sanitation, lack of safe water, living in a household with an infected person, and being a sexual partner of someone with acute hepatitis. The spread of hepatitis A can be reduced by adequate supplies of safe drinking water, proper disposal of sewage within communities, and personal hygiene practices such as regular hand washing before meals and after going to the bathroom.^[17]

Hepatitis B: Hepatitis B virus (HBV) damages the liver through acute and chronic infection, resulting from long-term consequences of chronic infection, principally cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. Approximately 80–90% of infants infected in the first year of life and 30–50% of children infected in the first 5 years of life will develop chronic infection, in comparison with only 5% of adults infected later in life. One in four people with chronic HBV infection is at risk of premature death from cirrhosis or liver cancer.^[18]

Hepatitis C: Hepatitis C virus (HCV) is a hepatotropic RNA virus that causes progressive liver damage, which might result in liver cirrhosis and HCC. Major risk factors are unsafe injection drug use and unsterile medical procedures (iatrogenic infections) in countries with high HCV prevalence. Diagnostic procedures include serum HCV antibody testing, HCV RNA measurement, viral genotype and subtype determination and, lately, assessment of resistance-associated substitutions. Direct-acting antiviral agents are available, which target three proteins involved in the HCV life cycle: the NS3/4A protease, the NS5A protein and the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase NS5B protein.^[19]

Hepatitis D: The hepatitis D virus (HDV) or delta hepatitis is the most difficult to treat and aggressive, with the most rapid evolution to cirrhosis, HCC, and death. Due to the dependence of HDV on the hepatitis B virus (HBV), it is likely that as HBV vaccination rates increase, the population vulnerable to HDV will decrease. There is currently no HDV vaccine, leaving those infected with HBV vulnerable to HDV. HDV utilizes the host for almost all its replicative cycle, leading to a paucity of true antiviral targets. Although not satisfactory, the mainstay of therapy thus far has been interferon alpha and liver transplant. It is hoped that the next decade will bring us substantially closer to meeting all unmet needs and closer towards the eradication of HDV.^[20]

Hepatitis E: Hepatitis E virus (HEV) infection can lead to acute and chronic hepatitis as well as to extrahepatic neurological and renal disease. Four genotypes are responsible for most infections in humans, of which HEV genotypes 1 and 2 are obligate human pathogens and HEV genotypes 3 and 4 are mostly zoonotic. HEV was considered an epidemic of acute hepatitis owing to contamination of drinking water supplies with human faeces. HEV is recognized as an endemic, and infections occur through zoonotic transmission or contaminated blood products in immunocompromised individuals. HEV infections can be diagnosed by measuring anti-HEV antibodies, HEV RNA or viral capsid antigen in blood or stool. An effective HEV vaccine is licensed for use in China and recently launched in India in August 2025 (Hevrevac).^[21]

(ii) Alcohol Related Liver Diseases (ALD)

It is to be understood that 12 fluid ounces of beer, four ounces of wine, or 1.5 fluid ounces of distilled spirits all contain approximately 14 g or 0.6 fluid ounces of pure alcohol. Based on this, the threshold for developing severe ALD in men is an intake of less than 60–80 g per day of alcohol for 10 years, while in women 20–40 g per day of alcohol. Furthermore, overexpression of TNF- α mRNA in the liver activates the liver cell functions, and macrophages and this causes the pro-inflammatory response and ROS elevation to reveal the liver toxicity. The mechanism of liver toxicity has been reported with activation of ROS, IL-6, and IL-8. In addition to this are the poorly understood hormonal factors, immunological, social, nutritional, and host factors. Chronic Hepatitis C (HCV) infection is one of the factors in the progression of ALD to cirrhosis in chronic and excessive drinkers.^[22]

Alcoholic fatty liver disease: Alcoholic fatty liver disease (AFLD) is the earliest stage of liver disease. Accumulation of triglycerides in the hepatocytes results from both increased inflow of free fatty acids (FFA) and lipogenesis within the liver. Fat accumulation in the liver is dependent mainly on recirculating FFAs from the adipose tissue pool. The visceral adipose tissue has a greater lipolytic potential than the subcutaneous adipose tissue. The release of FFA from visceral fat depots reaches the liver directly through the portal circulation. Increased oxidation of alcohol within the liver and resulting free radicals may cause injury to hepatocytes. Abstaining from alcohol will likely cause the fatty liver to subside.^[23]

Alcoholic hepatitis: Alcohol-related hepatitis (ARH), a form of ALD, is an acute inflammatory syndrome of jaundice and liver injury occurring in patients with significant alcohol use. The severity can range from subclinical to acute severe illness, which is associated with high mortality. Symptoms include abdominal pain, jaundice, and fever, and it is often associated with long-term heavy drinking. ARH can be resolved with abstinence and supportive therapy; however, these measures do not guarantee recovery in all patients.^[24]

Alcoholic cirrhosis: Several hypotheses about the mechanisms are acetaldehyde-induced toxic effects, generation of reactive oxygen species, direct or indirect hepatic stellate cells, activation by metabolites or inflammatory pathways. More recently, changes in the microbiota together with a permeable intestinal barrier are increasingly initiators of hepatic inflammation and fibrosis in patients with alcohol abuse. Treatment opportunities are very difficult unless the patient is willing to abstain from alcohol abuse. At the same time, it is worth mentioning the need to explore why some patients apparently not develop fibrosis or cirrhosis in the presence of alcohol abuse. It was reported that the existence of patients with the patatin-like phospholipase domain containing protein 3 (PNPLA3) polymorphism may be used as a marker of more rapid fibrogenesis.^[25]

(iii) Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is the most common chronic liver disease in North America and Europe, with increasing prevalence in other regions of the world. Its spectrum encompasses steatosis, NASH, fibrosis and cirrhosis. It is considered the manifestation of metabolic syndrome in the liver, and its development and progression are influenced by the complex interaction of environmental and genetic factors. It is necessary to understand the histopathological features, differential diagnoses, the commonly used grading and staging systems of NAFLD, NAFLD associated with other diseases, and recurrence or occurrence of NAFLD after liver transplantation.^[26]

(iv) Autoimmune Hepatic Diseases

Autoimmune hepatitis is characterized by necro-inflammation, primary biliary cholangitis and primary sclerosing cholangitis. The induction and perpetuation of autoimmunity are i) genetic predisposition ii) environmental factors iii) defects in immune regulation. The body's immune system mistakenly attacks and damages the liver, causing inflammation and swelling. Symptoms can range from fatigue, joint pain, and nausea to jaundice, though some people are asymptomatic. Treatment typically involves immunosuppressant medications, such as corticosteroids, to slow the immune response,

and in severe cases, a liver transplant may be necessary.^[27]

(v) Genetic & Metabolic Liver Disease

The genetic mutation causes a problem with the liver's ability to process nutrients like fats, proteins, or carbohydrates. These conditions can affect only the liver or other organs as well, and common examples include Wilson disease, Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency, and hereditary hemochromatosis. Symptoms include fatigue, nausea, jaundice, and liver failure. Diagnosis is made through a combination of medical history, physical exams, and various tests that can include blood gas analysis, organic acid analysis, and gene sequencing. Treatment depends on the specific condition including medication, dietary changes, or lifestyle adjustments.^[28]

(vi) Liver Cancer

The major liver cancer diseases are: **Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC)** - In the early stage, curative treatments such as surgical resection, liver transplant and local ablation can improve the patient's survival. Researchers have been investigating molecular biomarkers with high sensitivity and reliability as Golgi 73 protein (GP73), Glypican-3 (GPC3), Osteopontin (OPN), microRNAs and others. MicroRNAs can regulate important pathways in carcinogenesis, as tumour angiogenesis and progression. It is necessary to understand the recent advances related to the cause, treatment, biomarkers, clinical aspects, and outcome in hepatocellular carcinoma.^[29]

Cholangiocarcinoma

- Cholangiocarcinoma is a rare but highly aggressive malignancy of the biliary tract. Symptoms may be vague, especially when the neoplasm begins within the liver, and may include nonspecific symptoms like abdominal pain, weight loss, and fatigue. Extrahepatic tumors may present with jaundice or abdominal pain.^[30] **Metastatic liver cancer** - The liver is one of the most common sites for cancer metastasis, accounting for 25% of all cases. A variety of primary tumours may be the source of metastasis; however, colorectal adenocarcinomas are the most prominent topic of research in the literature, as they are the most common. The dual blood supply of the liver not only makes it uniquely susceptible to metastasis from gastrointestinal cancers but also accessible to

interventional therapies. Treatment strategies are rapidly evolving worldwide, with a movement towards an interprofessional approach for better outcomes.^[31]

TREATMENTS FOR LIVER DISEASES

Based on the type of liver disease, treatment strategies are followed as given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Treatments for liver diseases

LIFESTYLE MODIFICATIONS

Lifestyle modification involves altering long-term habits, typically of eating or physical activity and

maintaining the new behaviour for months or years. Table 1 describes what is to be adopted as a part of life cycle management in liver health.

Table 1: Life style modification strategy for liver health

Widely adopted	Occasionally adopted	Inconsistently adopted
Body weight reduction target		
Reduce body weight by $\geq 7-10\%$ to improve steatohepatitis/fibrosis	Reduce body weight by $\geq 3-7\%$ to improve steatosis	Reduce body weight by $\geq 7-10\%$ to improve steatosis.
Other recommendations		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase overall physical activity. • Restrict caloric intake. • Exercise 150-300 minutes/week of moderate intensity, 75-150 minutes of vigorous intensity, • Reduce consumption of commercially produced fructose. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider a low-carbohydrate diet. • Restrict saturated fat consumption. • Restrict alcohol consumption and reduce ultra-processed food intake • Follow the Mediterranean diet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider a low-fat diet. • Promote smoking cessation. • Avoid alcohol consumption. • Increase omega-3 fatty acid-rich food consumption • Increase fibre consumption. • Reduce processed meat-consumption

DRUG THERAPY FOR LIVER DISEASES

Drug therapy involves the administration of drugs to achieve a desired therapeutic effect, which may include symptom relief, disease modification or prevention of future illness. Drugs for liver diseases are categorized based on their:

- Mechanism of action (hepatoprotective and antiviral drugs) and
- Type of liver diseases used so far.

Hepatoprotective Drugs: ^[32,33] Hepatoprotective drugs are used to protect the liver from damage.

Herbal medicines demonstrate hepatoprotective effects by acting through several mechanisms, including antioxidant effects by eliminating free radicals and reducing oxidative stress, anti-inflammatory action by inhibiting inflammatory pathways and responses, detoxification by helping to clear toxic substances from the liver and hepatocyte membrane protection by protecting the liver cells from damage.

Liv.52 is an established ayurvedic polyherbal formulation containing the key ingredients such as Himsra, Kasani, Mandur Bhasma, Kakamachi, Arjuna, Kasamarda, Biranjasipha and Jhavuka. These ingredients are processed with other herbs like Eclipta alba and Phyllanthus amarus and formulated into a dosage form.

Silymarin is an active compound of Silybum marianum (L.) Garten., commonly known as “milk thistle”, is one of the oldest plants which has been commonly utilized for the treatment of liver diseases

Glycyrrhizin is a triterpenoid glycoside isolated from the root of Glycyrrhiza glabra L, commonly known as liquorice root, has been used in the traditional medicine systems of Nepal, India, China, and other countries for the treatment of jaundice

Andrographolide and neo-andrographolide are the active chemical constituents of the herbaceous plant of Andrographis paniculata, commonly known as “king of bitters” is well-known for liver diseases.

Picoside and kutkoside are the active chemical constituents of roots and rhizomes of Picrorhiza kurroa Royle, commonly known as “Kutki” or “Kutaki,” and have been used to treat hepatic disorders.

Curcumin is the principle curcuminoid found in the rhizome of Curcuma longa, commonly known as

“turmeric”. Traditional use of turmeric for the treatment of bilirubin-related liver disease, such as jaundice and several other hepatic complications.

Phyllanthin and hypophyllanthin are potent hepatoprotective lignans found in Phyllanthus niruri Linn., commonly known as “gale of the wind,” is a long-established herbal remedy for jaundice and other hepatic diseases

Berberine is an isoquinoline alkaloid which could be isolated from roots, rhizomes. stem, bark of Berberis aristata DC, commonly known as “barberry” has been used as tonic remedy for liver.

Embelin is chemically “2,5-dihydroxy-3-undecyl-1,4-benzoquinone,” is an active chemical constituent

of the leaves of Embelia ribes Burm.f. commonly known as “false black pepper” and is known for free radical scavenging and liver protective function.

Resveratrol is chemically “trans-3,5,4'-trihydroxystilbene” is a naturally occurring polyphenol compound present in grapes, blueberries and raspberries with potent antioxidant properties. Resveratrol, a phytoalexin, is generated in plants when bacteria and fungi attacked it. Resveratrol shows liver protection via reduction of oxidative stress during hepatocyte injury by modifying the expression of nuclear transcription factors Nrf2 and NF-κB and downregulating HO-1 and ion gene expression.

Anti-Viral Drugs:^[34] Antivirals work through various mechanisms, like inhibiting DNA synthesis, blocking viral entry or replication and interfering with viral enzymes crucial for the virus's life cycle. Major anti-viral drugs with respect to their benefits and drawbacks are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Anti-viral drugs used for liver diseases

Dosage form	Benefits	Drawbacks
Lamivudine 100 mg daily	First licensed agent and well established efficacy and safety record. Lower cost.	Highest incidence of resistant mutations of M204V/I substitution (20% at year 1, 70% at year 5)
Adefovir dipivoxil 10 mg daily	Low drug resistance rate and no cross resistance with nucleoside analogue	Incident of resistant mutation of N236T and A181V (29% at year 5). Prolonged treatment causes renal tubular acidosis with hypophosphodaemia.

Telbivudine 600 mg daily	Higher seroconversion rate	Incidence of resistant mutation of M204I mutation (5% at year 1). Myopathy and neuropathy.
Entecavir 1.0 mg daily	Anti HBV effect, Lowest rate of resistance	Incidence of resistance and mutation of T184G or M250V (1.2% at year5)
Tenofovir disoproxil 300 mg daily	More potent in reducing HBV load in patient with prior failure or resistant to lamivudine and adefovir.	Most expensive. No resistance mutations reported at year 3. Serious side effects on kidneys and bones and can cause liver problems in some cases

Drugs Based on Type of Liver Disease

The drugs used for liver diseases vary based on the type of disease. The choice of drugs is based on the types of liver diseases because the treatment efficiency depends on their respective mechanism of working. Below are typical examples of drugs and their mechanism.

Ademetionine is used in intrahepatic cholestasis associated with NAFLD, ALD, biliary cholangitis, cystic fibrosis and reduced bile formation. It maintains sufficient levels of glutathione, a key antioxidant, in the liver. Also improves bile flow from the liver and stabilizes liver function by its hepatoprotective effects.

Metadoxine is used in AFLD, ARH, NAFLD/NASH. It protects liver cells (hepatocytes) from harmful free radicals, increases the rate at which alcohol is eliminated from the blood and tissues, reducing the amount of time the liver is exposed to toxic substances, restores the cellular energy by increasing the levels of ATP and NADH in the liver, reduces fat accumulation and decreases fibronectin and procollagen, which causes liver scarring.

Ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) is the first-line medication for primary biliary cholangitis, treating cholestatic liver disease and cystic fibrosis, and dissolving cholesterol gallstones by reducing bile saturation and increasing cholesterol solubility. It has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects. Stabilizes liver cell membranes (anti-apoptotic), and promotes the secretion of bile. It alters the composition of the bile acid pool, making it more hydrophilic and less toxic to the liver, which stimulates the impaired biliary secretion.

Entecavir lowers the amount of HBV DNA in the body, leading to improvements in liver health and

reducing complications. Entecavir is a guanosine analogue that is activated inside liver cells. It then inhibits the hepatitis B virus's DNA polymerase, preventing the virus from making copies of itself.

Lamivudine suppresses HBV replication in the blood. It improves liver function by decreasing serum bilirubin and increasing serum albumin. Also reduces the risk of complications and is effective in preventing recurrent HBV infection after a liver transplant by improving post-transplant survival. Cellular uptake of the drug and phosphorylation into its active triphosphate form, lamivudine triphosphate (3TC-TP), competes with the cell's natural deoxycytidine triphosphate (dCTP) for incorporation into the growing viral DNA chain by the HBV DNA polymerase. Due to the Termination of the DNA chain, further elongation of the viral DNA chain is prevented.

Telbivudine effectively reduces the amount of HBV in the body and improves liver health to improve liver histology, resolution of inflammation, and reversal of fibrosis over time. Telbivudine has shown more potent viral suppression and higher response rates compared to older treatments like lamivudine. Telbivudine is a nucleoside analogue that acts as a reverse transcriptase inhibitor. It blocks the Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) from multiplying by interfering with the enzymes it uses to replicate its genetic material.

Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir combination is approved to treat specific types of chronic (long-term) hepatitis C infection in both adults and children aged 3 years and older. Mechanism: Glecaprevir is an NS3/4A protease inhibitor that works by reducing the amount of the Hepatitis C virus (HCV) in the body, and Pibrentasvir is an NS5A inhibitor that stops the virus from spreading within the body.

Sofosbuvir, Velpatasvir and Voxilaprevir combination is a potent DAA regimen for treating chronic HCV in patients whose infections were resistant to prior treatments, including those who previously used sofosbuvir and velpatasvir. The drug combination works by disrupting the HCV life cycle at multiple stages. Sofosbuvir (a nucleotide analog polymerase inhibitor) inhibits the viral RNA polymerase (NS5B), which is essential for HCV replication. Velpatasvir is an NS5A inhibitor, targets the NS5A protein, a viral protein crucial for viral RNA replication and virion assembly. Voxilaprevir is a protease inhibitor that blocks the HCV NS3/4A protease, which is necessary for processing viral proteins into functional viral particles.

Methionine is essential for synthesizing glutathione (GSH), a primary antioxidant that protects the liver from damage caused by free radicals generated during alcohol metabolism. Adequate methionine can help improve liver enzyme levels (e.g., AST, ALT, GGT), which often become elevated in liver diseases like viral hepatitis and alcoholic liver disease. Methionine is converted by the enzyme methionine adenosyltransferase (MAT) into S-adenosylmethionine (SAME), which is crucial for the methylation of DNA, proteins, lipids, and other molecules vital for normal liver function.

Interferons are used in viral hepatitis B & C. Alpha-IFN stops viral replication, reduces inflammation, and prevents cancer (HCC) and also plays complex roles in NAFLD & fibrosis via immune regulation, but high doses can cause liver toxicity. Interferons boost innate immune responses, directly inhibit viral replication, and modulate adaptive immunity to clear infections.

SURGICAL THERAPY

Hepatic Resection (Hepatectomy)

Hepatic resection, also known as hepatectomy, is a surgical procedure to remove part or all of the liver. It is primarily used to treat liver tumours, both primary which originate in the liver, and secondary, which spread from other organs. It can also be a part of living donor liver transplantation, where a portion of the liver is resected from a healthy donor. Mortality rates as high as 25% are reported following hepatic resection (i.e., partial resection of the liver) in patients with cirrhosis. Risk stratification based on the Child

class and MELD score has allowed more appropriate selection of patients, thus leading to lower mortality rates. In an analysis of 82 cirrhotic patients who underwent hepatic resection, the perioperative mortality rate was 29% in patients with a MELD score ≥ 9 but 0% in those with a MELD score ≤ 8 . In addition to predicting mortality, the MELD score can predict morbidity after liver resection. In one study, the frequency of post-liver resection liver failure was 0%, 3.6%, and 37.5% in patients with MELD scores of less than 9, 9–10, and greater than 10, respectively.^[35]

Liver Transplant

A liver transplant is a surgical procedure to replace a diseased liver with a healthy one from a donor. Liver transplant (LT) is indicated in cases of acute or chronic end-stage liver disease where medical therapy has failed. Patients who experience hepatic decompensation, such as hepatic encephalopathy, variceal haemorrhage, or ascites, should first undergo medical management. If they are potential LT candidates, a thorough transplant evaluation should be initiated. Notably, up to 80% of LTs are performed for decompensated cirrhosis. Patients with cirrhosis are typically classified using the Child-Turcotte-Pugh score, which integrates both biochemical markers (serum albumin, serum bilirubin, and International Normalized Ratio [INR]) and clinical findings (ascites and encephalopathy) to estimate prognosis and guide management.^[36]

Laparoscopic Liver Surgery

Laparoscopic liver surgery is a minimally invasive procedure to treat liver issues like cysts or tumors, using small incisions, a camera, and special instruments instead of a large open incision. This approach typically results in less pain, a shorter hospital stay, faster recovery, and minimal scarring compared to open surgery. It is used for both benign and complex malignant conditions, and robotic-assisted versions are also becoming more common. A surgeon makes several small "keyhole" incisions in the abdomen instead of one large one. A laparoscope (a camera) is inserted through one incision to provide a high-definition view of the liver on a monitor for the surgeon. Long, thin surgical instruments are used through the other incisions to perform the procedure. The surgeon can then perform a liver resection, where

a part of the liver (a lobe or a segment) is removed. Robotic arms can be used to enhance the precision and dexterity of the instruments. The benefits of this surgery are faster recovery, less pain, shorter hospital stay and minimal scarring.^[37]

TARGETED THERAPIES

Targeted therapies for liver disease are showing promise, with new drugs and approaches focusing on specific mechanisms within the liver to improve outcomes. These mainly include therapies for non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), the most common type of liver cancer.^[38]

Targeting Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver by FXR Agonist^[39]

FXR agonist drugs are a class of synthetic medications that bind to activate the FXR, a nuclear receptor that regulates processes like bile acid homeostasis, lipid and glucose metabolism, and immune responses. These drugs are used to treat conditions such as primary biliary cholangitis (PBC) and NAFLD/NASH. Ex. Obeticholic acid, cilofexor, fexaramine, firsocostat and tropifexor.

Targeting Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver by PPAR agonists

Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptors (PPAR) agonists are a class of drugs that activate, which are nuclear receptors that regulate the expression of genes involved in metabolism and inflammation. PPAR agonists bind to specific PPAR receptor isoforms (α , γ , and δ). Different agonists target different PPAR isoforms and are used for various conditions. This binding activates the PPARs, which then act as transcription factors, controlling the expression of genes involved in lipid metabolism, glucose homeostasis, and inflammation. PPAR δ agonists are used to treat primary biliary cholangitis. Ex. Seladelpar, elafibranor (dual agonist).^[40]

Targeting Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver by CCR2/CCR5 inhibitors

Cenicriviroc (CVC) is a first-in-class, oral, dual CCR2/CCR5 antagonist with potent anti-

inflammatory and antifibrotic activity currently in clinical development for the treatment of liver fibrosis associated with NASH. The recruitment of inflammatory monocytes and macrophages via chemokine receptor CCR2, as well as of lymphocytes and hepatic stellate cells via CCR5, promotes the progression of NASH to fibrosis.^[41]

Targeting Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver by THR- β agonists

A THR-beta agonist is a type of drug that binds to and activates the thyroid hormone receptor-beta (THR- β), a protein that regulates gene expression, and is primarily used to treat metabolic liver diseases like NASH. These drugs are designed to target the liver, promoting processes like fatty acid oxidation and reducing liver fat, while minimizing systemic side effects on the heart or bones. Ex. Resmetirom. FDA approved resmetirom (Rezdiffra) in the U.S. on March 14, 2024, for adults with noncirrhotic MASH (formerly NASH) who have moderate to advanced liver scarring (fibrosis). It is the first and only drug approved for this condition and is intended in conjunction with diet and exercise.^[42,43]

Targeting Hepatocellular Carcinoma using Tyrosine kinase inhibitors

Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors (TKIs) are a class of targeted therapy drugs that block tyrosine kinase enzymes. Many TKIs are designed as "precision medicine" based on the genetic makeup of a patient's tumor. TKIs work by blocking the active site of these enzymes, preventing them from adding phosphate groups to their target proteins. This blockage stops the downstream signaling cascade, which prevents the cell from getting the signals to grow and divide, thereby inhibiting cancer cell growth. Ex. Imatinib (Glivec®), erlotinib (Tarceva®), dasatinib (Sprycel®), and gefitinib (Iressa®). Sorafenib and regorafenib are multi-kinase inhibitors that target proteins involved in liver tumour growth and blood vessel formation. Other approved kinase inhibitors include Lenvatinib (2018), Cabozantinib (2019) and Regorafenib (2017), which targets angiogenic, stromal, and oncogenic kinases.^[44,45]

Immunotherapy using a Checkpoint inhibitors

Immunotherapy for liver cancer uses the body's own immune system to fight cancer cells, with checkpoint inhibitors. Checkpoint inhibitor drugs work by "releasing the brakes" on the immune system, specifically T-cells, allowing them to recognize and attack cancer cells more effectively. They block proteins that prevent the immune system from attacking cancer cells. They target proteins like PD-1, PD-L1, and CTLA-4, which normally suppress the immune system to prevent it from attacking the body's own cells. Liver cancer creates an immunosuppressed environment by recruiting cells that prevent T-cells from attacking. Checkpoint inhibitors help reverse this, reactivating the immune response against the tumor. Immunotherapy is often used in combination with other treatments like chemotherapy or targeted therapy to improve outcomes. For advanced liver cancer, a combination of atezolizumab (a checkpoint inhibitor) and bevacizumab (a targeted antibody) is often used as a first-line treatment, according to the American Cancer Society and Cancer Research UK. Tremelimumab can also be used in combination with durvalumab in certain cases. Liver has a unique immune microenvironment that can make immunotherapy less effective. Researchers are working to overcome these challenges through new strategies and combinations.^[46]

EMERGING THERAPIES

Histotripsy

This technology is approved by the FDA and is a non-invasive, non-thermal treatment for liver tumors that uses focused ultrasound waves to mechanically disrupt and destroy cancer cells. It is used in patients who are not candidates for surgery or radiation. The destroyed tissue is absorbed by the body over time. Histotripsy works through a process called cavitation (air pockets). The focused energy created by the ultrasound machine generates enough force to pulverize liver tumour tissue. It also creates a "bubble cloud" in the process, which shows us that the energy has reached the level necessary to destroy tumour cells. Patients receiving histotripsy are given general anaesthesia to control their breathing and minimize movement of the targeted tumour(s). Then, they're securely positioned on the operating room table, and the equipment is situated over them. Doctors then

program the robot to deliver the planned treatment. Once the machine is activated, the procedure itself may take anywhere from 10 to 50 minutes per tumour. The focused energy travels through the body to its targeted location and is automatically delivered. Unlike thermal methods, histotripsy is thought to preserve tumour antigens, which may stimulate an immune response to help the body clear the destroyed cells and fight remaining cancer.^[47]

Regenerative medicine and cell therapies

Advancements in the field of regenerative medicine open up new horizons and raise hope in the treatment of irreversibly damaged liver cirrhosis. Moreover, compared to current operative therapies, it is less invasive, less expensive, and avoids the problem of a shortage of donors, immune rejection, and other similar complications. Ideally, liver regenerative medicine seems an ultimate solution for liver cirrhosis. Liver regenerative medicine uses various approaches based on cell therapy and tissue or organ engineering, and direct reprogramming. Cell-based therapy is defined as the transplantation of cells from different sources, like primary hepatocytes, mesenchymal stromal cells, stem cells (induced pluripotent stem cells, embryonic stem cells, hepatic progenitor cells), to improve liver function. Transplantation of mature hepatocytes and liver stem/progenitor cells (LSPCs) from allogeneic sources is already in clinical trials. Researchers are trying to refine protocols for proliferation, differentiation, and storage of these cells to have them in plenty and always ready to be transplanted. The other approach mainly covers the area of liver tissue or organ engineering, engraftment, and monitoring in patients. Ongoing therapeutic approaches in tissue engineering include implantable constructs of hepatic tissues and whole organs. For the construction of hepatic tissues, natural and synthetic bioactive scaffolds are designed. Nanotechnology and microchip devices are contributing a lot in this field. Moreover, whole organ engineering is also in great focus to escape end-stage liver diseases. However, the determination of ideal cell types, cell volume, and optimal seeding techniques is yet to be discovered.^[48,49]

Directing the gut-liver axis or specific pathways

Currently, lifestyle interventions are the most essential and effective strategies for preventing and controlling NAFL without the development of fibrosis. While there are still limited appropriate drugs specifically to treat NAFL/NASH, growing progress is being seen in elucidating the pathogenesis and identifying therapeutic targets. The gut-liver axis is widely implicated in the pathogenesis of liver diseases, where it is increasingly the focus of clinical research. The armamentarium for targeting the gut-liver axis will continue to expand. Further clinical trials, translated from our current knowledge of the gut-liver axis, promise an exciting future in liver treatment.^[50] Importantly, growing evidence elucidates that the disruption of the gut–liver axis and microbe-derived metabolites drives the pathogenesis of NAFL or NASH. Extracellular vesicles (EVs) act as a signalling mediator, resulting in lipid accumulation, macrophage and hepatic stellate cell activation, further promoting inflammation and liver fibrosis progression during the development of NAFL or NASH. Targeting gut microbiota or EVs may serve as new strategies for the treatment of NAFL or NASH.^[51] These targeted therapies represent a shift towards more personalized and effective approaches to managing liver diseases, with the potential to improve outcomes for a wide range of patients.

ADVANCED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Recently, several drug delivery systems have been developed using advanced techniques for more convenient, controlled, and targeted delivery to the liver. Each drug delivery system has its own peculiarities that determine its release rate and mechanism. This is largely due to the differences in the physical, chemical, and morphological characteristics, which will ultimately affect their affinities for various drug substances to liver cells or tissues. Studies on these have identified diffusion, chemical reaction, solvent reaction, and stimulus control as major release mechanisms. For instance, since most cancer cells can proliferate through porous blood vessels and lymphatic system, the drug can easily permeate through this opening to reach the target tissues. This is referred to as enhanced permeability and retention (EPR). EPR is a passive diffusion mechanism well researched and applied in the delivery of many chemotherapeutic agents.

Although EPR is a controversial concept, this effect has been observed by many researchers in various types of human tumours and is the basis for the use of nano-medicine in cancer treatment. These delivery systems can also reach the target cells through the control of one or more physical or chemical properties in the process of responsive stimuli targeting. These physical properties include pH, temperature, ultrasound, magnetic and electric fields.^[52] The advanced drug delivery system is designed as a modified or targeted drug delivery system

MODIFIED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

Modified drug delivery systems for liver diseases encompass several advanced platforms tailored to improve therapeutic outcomes by enhancing targeting, release control, and minimizing side effects. It is a method of delivering drugs at a predetermined rate, maintaining therapeutic levels within a therapeutic window over an extended period, and targeting specific sites in the body. Various types of controlled drug delivery systems for liver diseases are given below.^[53]

Lipid based formulations^[54-57]

Liposomes are small lipid vesicles that encapsulate drugs, allowing non-immunogenic and modifiable delivery, widely used for treating ALD, hepatitis, cirrhosis, and HCC. Moreover, liposomes can reduce the amount of drug that penetrates healthy tissues, which is a major cause of cytotoxicity. They carry drugs such as rolipram, silymarin, astaxanthin, mangifera, saikosaponin D, doxorubicin, and sorafenib, utilizing passive and active targeting mechanisms based on particle size, charge, and ligand interactions, which improve drug bioavailability and reduce systemic toxicity. Micelles are similar to liposomes, designed mainly for the delivery of hydrophobic drugs. The asialoglycoprotein receptor is abundant in hepatocytes, minimally expressed in extra-hepatic tissues, and provides attractive advantages for hepatocyte-mediated delivery. In one of study, used a novel glycosylated derivative ligand to enhance drug liver-targeting delivery. For NAFL and NASH, nanoliposomes and polymer-lipid hybrid nanoparticles deliver agents such as statins, bilirubin, and vitamin E to reduce hepatic fat accumulation, inflammation, and oxidative stress. In alcoholic liver

disease, pH-sensitive and fusogenic liposomes carrying TNF- α inhibitors or rolipram effectively suppress liver inflammation, steatosis, and cell death by targeting hepatic macrophages and hepatocytes. Viral hepatitis treatment benefits from PEGylated liposomes and metal nanoparticles delivering antiviral drugs like interferons, enhancing therapeutic uptake and minimizing systemic side effects. For HCC, liposomal and PEGylated nanoparticles provide targeted chemotherapy delivery to tumour cells, reducing toxicity to healthy tissue. In liver fibrosis and cirrhosis, liposomal vitamin A targets hepatic stellate cells to deliver antifibrotic drugs and halt fibrosis progression. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) encapsulate drugs such as insulin and amphotericin B to improve controlled release and protect against premature degradation in drug-induced liver injury. These lipid-based formulations optimize drug delivery to diseased liver tissues, enhancing treatment outcomes across a range of liver conditions.

Exosomes

Exosomes are natural nanovesicles carrying endogenous cargo (proteins, nucleic acids); they can be engineered to carry drugs but face challenges in standardization. These are derived from biological sources, have been explored in ALD, NAFLD, and liver cancer for their innate ability to modulate immunity and deliver therapeutic cargo such as LGG-derived (*Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG) or ginger exosomes. Their endogenous nature supports both therapy and diagnostic potential.^[58]

Polymeric and Non-Lipid Nanoparticles

Polymeric nanoparticles serve important roles in delivering agents like tannic acid, vitamin E, superoxide dismutase, nucleoside drugs against hepatitis B virus, siRNA, and gene therapies for ALD, viral hepatitis, liver fibrosis, and HCC. These nanoparticles provide controlled release and surface functionalization, enabling precise therapeutic delivery and targeting genes or specific liver cells. Metallic and ceramic nanoparticles made of gold, silver, iron, and silica are used to deliver drugs or genes in hepatitis, HCC, and liver fibrosis. They offer tumour targeting, imaging capabilities, and antimicrobial effects through passive and active mechanisms, including magnetic targeting. They can

pose risks due to non-biodegradability and potential cytotoxicity. Ceramic nanoparticles are highly modifiable for specific delivery and used for resistant pH conditions, but may be cytotoxic.^[59-61]

Biological Carriers

Biological carriers improve the specificity and effectiveness of the delivery of drugs, proteins, or genetic material to diseased liver tissue. Protein-based carriers can be designed to exploit specific liver cell receptors, enabling targeted therapy for hepatitis, fibrosis, or hepatic cancers. Polysaccharides and lipids offer biocompatibility and flexible modification, allowing tailored therapies with reduced systemic toxicity. Hydrogels aid in regenerative medicine applications. Transporters like the SLC family underpin drug absorption, distribution, and efficacy in various hepatic conditions.^[62]

Bacterial platforms

Some bioengineered bacteria show natural tropism to the liver and can deliver drugs on-site, but there is a risk of immunogenicity and infection. Bacterial systems, although less common, are engineered to produce therapeutic cytokines like IL-22 locally in ALD through site-specific colonization.

Viral Vectors

Adeno-associated viruses (AAV), are used for gene delivery in ALD, hepatitis, and HCC, enabling efficient liver cell targeting and genetic modulation by transferring microRNAs and gene constructs, but are limited by possible immune response.

Drug-eluting beads or microspheres

For localized treatment of HCC, microspheres loaded with chemotherapeutics such as doxorubicin, gemcitabine, mitoxantrone, and irinotecan are administered via trans arterial chemoembolization, allowing controlled drug release directly into the tumour with minimal systemic exposure.

Conjugation approaches

PEGylation is applied in hepatitis B and liver fibrosis therapies to extend drug half-life and reduce

immunogenicity, as seen with PEG-interferon- α and PEG-FGF21. These platforms collectively represent a diverse and evolving toolkit for controlled drug delivery tailored to specific liver diseases, many of which are supported by ongoing preclinical and clinical research.^[63]

pH-Sensitive Nanoparticles and Sequential Delivery Systems

In liver cancer therapy, the pH-sensitive nanoparticles release the drug in response to the acidic microenvironment of tumours. In sequential drug delivery, timed or multi-stage release platforms are used, e.g., combinations targeting both inflammation and fibrosis, or combining gene/drug therapy.

Smart and responsive drug delivery system

SDDSs can preferentially accumulate and bind to the disease target, allowing for controlled release. The loaded medicines can act “smart” by inheriting from the controlled release. SDDSs are designed to take advantage of the different conditions (e.g., temperature, pH, and enzyme concentration) that occur in pathological tissues rather than in normal tissues in a “smart” way, enabling them to trigger drug release in the targeted tissue, overcome intermediate barriers, and increase bioavailability, blood circulation time, and overall therapeutic efficacy. A better understanding of tumour biology, combined with the increased availability of versatile materials such as polymers, lipids, inorganic carriers, polymeric hydrogels, and bio-macromolecular scaffolds, has led to the development of systems that can deliver chemotherapeutics to tumour sites with improved therapeutic efficacy in recent years.^[64]

Gene-Based and Immunotherapy

Delivery of genetic material with viral vectors or nanoparticles promising, especially for hereditary liver diseases or fibrosis. Currently, gene therapy is an area that exists predominantly in research laboratories, and its application is still experimental. Most trials are conducted in the United States, Europe, and Australia. The approach is broad,

with potential treatment of diseases caused by recessive gene disorders (cystic fibrosis, haemophilia, muscular dystrophy, and sickle cell anaemia), acquired genetic diseases such as cancer, and certain viral infections, such as AIDS. The ability to make local modifications in the human genome has been the objective of medicine since the discovery of DNA as the basic unit of heredity. Gene therapy is understood as the capacity for gene improvement by means of the correction of altered (mutated) genes or site-specific modifications that have treatment as a target. Further on, different strategies are described, which are often used for this purpose. One of the most often used techniques consists of recombinant DNA technology, in which the gene of interest or healthy gene is inserted into a vector, which can be a plasmidial, nanostructured, or viral; the latter is the most often used due to its efficiency in invading cells and introducing its genetic material.^[65]

Nanoparticles delivering antigens or immunomodulatory drugs, targeting immune cells in the liver, such as liver sinusoidal endothelial cells (LSECs).

LIVER TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

It is the method of treatment that involves the transportation of the therapeutic agent to the liver tissue or the infected part of the liver without reaching the remaining part of the body. This offers an improved efficacy of treatment and reduces side effects. The disadvantages include, complex design and manufacturing increase production costs; delivery systems may be cleared by immune cells, reducing efficacy; precise control of release rates is challenging; targeting efficiency can be affected by competition with natural ligands and immune reactions from carrier materials. Drug targeting to the liver requires four principles: the ability to load the drug, avoid degradation by body fluids, reach the target liver site and release the drug at the specific site at the predetermined time.^[66] Figure 4 represents drug targeting strategies.

Figure 4: Drug targeting

Active Targeting

In general, drug targeting can be achieved by passive and active strategies. Active targeting is a particular ligand-receptor type interaction that relies on the biological interface between target cells and the ligands attached to nanoparticles. Active targeting utilizes surface conjugation with a cell-specific ligand such as a peptide, protein, antibody, or carbohydrate, which binds to the corresponding receptor at the cell membrane.^[67] Viral vectors such as various subtypes of adeno-associated virus have obvious hepatic tropism and can be used as drug delivery vehicles when targeting nucleic acid drugs targeting the liver. Receptors overexpressed on the surface of hepatocytes include asialoglycoprotein receptors (ASGPR), glycyrrhizin acid receptors (GaR), transferrin receptors (TfR), and folate receptors (FR). Specific ligands developed against these receptors can be used to construct active targeted drug delivery systems, enhancing the targeting specificity of drugs for liver cancer cells. For example, conjugating nanoparticles containing ligands that recognize ASGPR with chemotherapeutic drugs can enable precise drug accumulation in liver cancer cells, thereby improving therapeutic efficacy. Active targeting strategies enable targeted drug delivery to hepatocytes, thereby increasing drug concentration within the target area and potentially enhancing efficacy while reducing toxicity. Numerous carrier materials are currently under investigation in preclinical studies; however, the attainment of their anticipated performance remains uncertain.^[67]

Passive targeting

The passive accumulation of nanoparticles at a specific body site relies on certain anatomic or pathophysiological features complementing the nanoparticle properties. Passive targeting relies on nanomedicines naturally accumulating in the liver due to the organ's vascular structure (e.g., Kupffer cell uptake of nanoparticles). The accumulation of nanoparticles within tumour tissue is due to the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect and the specific tumour microenvironment, and it also depends on the physicochemical properties of the carrier (such as shape, size, and carrier surface) and important characteristics of cancer cells (such as temperature, pH, and tumour cell surface charge). This approach offers the advantages of simplicity and broad applicability; however, due to limitations imposed by nanoparticle size, its targeting efficacy can be inconsistent, hindering precise target engagement.

Both the active and passive targeting approaches have the advantage of being more directed to a specific liver cell type that is relevant to a disease while reducing the side effects on other liver cell types. Modern targeting technologies often combine both strategies to first facilitate general (passive) liver uptake and subsequently ligand-mediated (active) cellular internalization for efficient and precise treatment.^[68]

Inverse Targeting and Inverse Agonist

The liver, as part of the reticuloendothelial system (RES), naturally filters and removes foreign particles like nanoparticles from the bloodstream. This process can be a major barrier to systemic drug delivery, as

therapeutics intended for other organs or tissues are cleared before they can have their desired effect. The inverse targeting approach is by administering certain sugar polymers or lipid microemulsions that saturate the RES (primarily the liver's Kupffer cells) before administering a therapeutic compound of interest, shifting its bio-distribution pattern. It is applied for treating extrahepatic diseases and preventing high drug accumulation in the liver to reduce hepatotoxicity (liver damage) caused by potent drugs. In certain scenarios, inverse targeting is used to prevent drug uptake by one cell type, such as Kupffer cells, to increase its availability for another type of liver cell, such as hepatic stellate cells or hepatocytes. For example, studies have shown that by inhibiting Kupffer cells, other antifibrotic therapies can more effectively reach the activated stellate cells that cause liver fibrosis. For liver cancer, some therapies may require inverse targeting to prevent off-target uptake. Researchers have used biomimetic nanoparticles coated with cell membranes to evade immune detection, allowing for more specific targeting of tumour cells. Further, inverse agonists are a type of pharmacological agent that bind to a receptor and reduce its constitutive (basal) activity, rather than simply blocking it like an antagonist. Ex. LXR inverse agonists are a liver-specific inverse agonist for the liver X Receptor (LXR), which has been developed to treat liver diseases like metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH). This approach was shown to suppress lipogenesis and inflammation in the liver.

Ligand-mediated targeting

Targeting ligands play a crucial role in distinguishing between pathological and normal tissues, specifically bind to receptors expressed on tumour cells, minimizing the damage caused by cytotoxic drugs to normal cells. Despite their diverse targets and entry mechanisms into tumour cells, this system enables selective delivery of drugs to cancer cells, significantly enhancing therapeutic efficacy while reducing toxicity. In recent years, several targeting ligands, including folic acid, carbohydrates, peptides, aptamers, and antibodies, have been utilized in targeted drug delivery systems. These targeting ligands accurately recognize and specifically bind to markers expressed on targeted tumour cells. The

successful use of these targeted drug delivery systems has effectively enhanced the therapeutic efficacy of cytotoxic drugs and reduced their toxic side effects. This innovation is being actively developed globally and is expected to revolutionize current cancer treatment strategies.^[69,70]

Physical Targeting

Lifestyle modifications focus on overall health to manage conditions like fatty liver disease. Lifestyle and general physical strategies include exercise, like aerobic activities such as walking, cycling, jogging, and swimming improve oxygen delivery to the liver and body; diet like a balanced diet rich in fruits, vegetables, and lean protein; and weight management is recommended.

Dual targeting

Dual targeting for liver disease involves strategies that focus on two different aspects of the disease simultaneously, often using nanocarriers to deliver therapies to specific cell types or subcellular organelles. These strategies can target both the liver and its cellular components, such as hepatocytes and mitochondria, or address both liver fibrosis and cardiovascular disease in patients with conditions like obesity and diabetes. Dual pharmacological agents, histone deacetylase (HDAC) and phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5) can inhibit liver disease progression, particularly in models of biliary inflammation and fibrosis. Icosabutate is a novel treatment that can simultaneously target liver fibrosis and atherosclerosis (artery clogging), making it a promising therapy for patients with both liver and heart disease. Astaxanthin (AXT) nanoparticles are designed to target both hepatocytes and mitochondria. Macrophage-disguised and apolipoprotein A-I-decorated liposomes can target both the liver and adipose tissue, delivering drugs to manage metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) and obesity.

Double Targeting

It refers to using therapeutic strategies that simultaneously target two different components of the liver, such as two cell types or two different molecular markers. Targeting two components can lead

to improved efficacy, overcoming resistance, broader treatment scope and enhanced drug delivery. For general liver diseases, nanoparticles can be modified with two different ligands, such as transferrin and mannan, to simultaneously target different types of liver cells, like Kupffer cells and cancer cells, for improved gene delivery. For liver cirrhosis, targets both hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) and macrophages, which play critical roles in the disease.

CONCLUSION

The global liver disease therapeutics market size was estimated at approximately USD 23.42 billion in 2025 and is projected to reach USD 33.84 billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR of 7.63%. Recent advancements in drug delivery techniques for hepatic diseases mark a pivotal shift in the management of liver conditions by enhancing therapeutic efficacy and minimizing systemic toxicity through targeted strategies. Current treatments have evolved from broad-spectrum pharmaceuticals to more innovative nanoparticle-based systems, which allow precise delivery to affected hepatic cells. Formulation breakthroughs such as liposomes, nano-emulsions, and polymeric nanoparticles have enabled greater specificity and improved patient outcomes in chronic and acute liver diseases. Future success in hepatic drug delivery will depend on integrating next-generation formulation science, precision targeting enabled by metabolic insights, and adaptive market strategies that accelerate development and widen global access. Despite ongoing regulatory and translational challenges, the collaboration of clinicians, researchers, and the pharmaceutical industry; coupled with advances in genetic engineering, regenerative biology and cellular therapies, is key to advancing this promising field. AI-driven diagnostics and the development of in vitro models, such as liver organoids, offer promising platforms for earlier detection and personalized treatment strategies. By addressing the limitations and confounders in current diagnostic and therapeutic approaches, future studies can further enhance patient outcomes and advance the field of hepatology. It can be concluded that understanding the complexities and challenges in the thrust area of liver research will nurture an improved or new path for treating various liver-associated disorders in the future.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors extend their sincere gratitude and appreciation to Dr. V. Ravichandiran, Ph.D., and Dr. K. Kannan, Ph.D., for the initiation of the Centre of Excellence in Hepatic Research (CEHR) and their constructive criticism and thoughtful insights in this area of research.

REFERENCES

1. Kalra A, Jetiskul E, Wehrle CJ, Tuma F. Physiology, Liver. 2023, In: StatPearls.Treasure Island (FL): Stat Pearls Publishing.
2. Padmanaban SM, Baek JW, & Charanthy SS, Chandrasekaran S, et.al. Nanoparticle-based therapeutic strategies for chronic liver disease: Advanced insights. *Liver Research*, 2025; 9(2):104–117.
3. Vijayan V, Unagolla JM, Panchal D, John JE, Menon SS, Menon JU. Biomimetic nanoparticles for targeted therapy of liver disease. *RSC Pharm.*, 2025; 2(5):667-682.
4. Ross and Wilson. *Human Anatomy and Physiology*, 2014; 12th edition, Chapter 12:308-309
5. Ozougwu JC. Physiology of Liver. *International Journal of Research and Biosciences*, 2017; 4(8):13-24
6. Peter J. Bazira, *Anatomy of the liver. Surgery(Oxford) Elsevier*, 2023, 41(6): 313-318
7. Mohajan HK, *Anatomy of Human Liver: A Theoretical Study*, *Journal of Innovations in Medical Research*, 2025; 4(1):17-23
8. Can Gan, Yuan Yuan, Haiyuan Shen, Jinhang Gao, et.al., *Liver diseases: epidemiology, causes, trends and predictions*, *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*, 2025; 10(33):1-36.
9. Malin Fromme, Pavel Strnad, *Pathophysiology of Chronic Liver Disease Development*, *International Journal of Molecular Science*, 2022; 23(6) 3385:1-3. DOI:10.3390/ijms 23063385.
10. Phang-Lyn S, Llerena VA. *Biochemistry, Biotransformation*. In: StatPearls.Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing, 2025.
11. Nazi Y. *The Role of Phase I and Phase II Metabolic Pathways in Pharmacokinetics*. *Journal of Pharmacological Reports*, 2024; 8(3):1-2

12. Almazroo OA, Miah MK, Venkataramanan R. Drug Metabolism in the Liver. *Clin Liver Dis.*, 2017; (1):1-20.
13. Mohsin N u A, Farrukh M, Shahzadi S, Irfan M. Drug Metabolism: Phase I and Phase II Metabolic Pathways. *Drug Metabolism and Pharmacokinetics*, Intech Open, 2024.
14. O'Brien L, Hosick PA, John K, Stec DE, Hinds TD. Biliverdin reductase isozymes in metabolism. *Trends Endocrinol Metab.*, 2015; 4:212-220.
15. Stec DE, John K, Trabbic CJ, Luniwal A, Hankins MW, Baum J, Hinds TD. Bilirubin Binding to PPAR α Inhibits Lipid Accumulation, 2016; *PLoS One*: 1-17.
16. Babak Abdinia, Maryam.S Evaluation of the causes and diagnosis of acute hepatitis, 2024; 12(9): 1-4.
17. Tekalign Wolde Hana Uno. Hepatitis A review. *Int J Adv Multidiscip Res.*, 2019; 6(8):24-31.
18. Ashworth M. Global, regional, and national burden of hepatitis B, 1990–2019: Disease Study, 2019; *Cubical Medical Science*. 2022; 7(3):796-829.
19. Michael P. Manns, Maria Buti, *Nature Reviews Disease Primers*, 2017;3(1):17006:1-19
20. Theo Heller, Maria Buti, Pietro Hepatitis D *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology*,2023; 21(8):2051-2064.
21. Kamar N, Izopet J, Pavio N, Aggarwal R, Labrique A, Wedemeyer H, Dalton HR. Hepatitis E virus infection. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*, 2017; 3:17086.
22. Verniselvan S, Charavasan S. Toxicology report [ALDJ]. *Toxicology Report*. 2021; 8:376-385.
23. Chaye Gobalan, *Biology of cardiovascular & metabolic diseases*, 2022; chapter 11:195-208
24. H.Chaudhry, AlamSohal, Marina Roytman. Alcohol related liver disease, 2023; 29(17):2551-2570
25. Keshunobich D, Gutierrez Reyes DG. *Liver Pathophysiology*, 2017; Science Direct.
26. Chen YY, Yeh MM. Pathological features and molecular mechanisms of hepatocarcinogenesis. *J Formos Med Assoc.*, 2022; 121(6):1131-1141.
27. Annarosa Florean, Nora cazzagon. Autoimmune liver Disease, 2019;59:1-7
28. Serafotezi B, Bachtnezi, Adeyi AA. *Diagnostic Histopathology – Metabolic Disorders of Liver*, 2014; 20(3):125-133.
29. Tunissiolli NM, Pavarino EC, Hepatocellular carcinoma. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*, 2017; 18(4):863-872.19.
30. Menon G, Subash C, Roy P. Cholangiocarcinoma. In: *StatPearls.Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024: NCBI Bookshelf*
31. Griscom JT, Wolf PS. *Liver metastasis*,2023; Book ID: NBK553118
32. Pandey B, Baral R, Kaundinnayana A, et al. Promising hepatoprotective agents from the natural sources: a study of scientific evidence. *Egypt Liver Journal*, 2023; 13(14).1-26.
33. Mancak M, Altintas D, Balaban Y, Koca Caliskan U. Evidence-based herbal treatments in liver diseases. *Hepato Forum*, 2024; 5(1):50-60.
34. Li-Ping Chen, Jun Zhao.et al. Antiviral treatment to prevent chronic hepatitis B or C related hepatocellular carcinoma, 2012;1(6):174–183.
35. Friedman LS. Surgery in patient with liver disease. *Transactions of the American Clinical and Climatological Association*, 2010; 121:192–205.
36. Dabanesh Y. Mousa OY. *National library of Medicine. Liver transplantation*, 2025; Book Id: NBK559161.
37. Kwon IS, Yun SS, Lee D. Laparoscopic liver resection for malignant tumours. *J Korean Surg Soc.*, 2012;83(1):30-35.
38. Jo P. Targeting Liver Disorders through the Drug Delivery System. *J Dev Drugs*, 2022;11(3):1
39. Carey EJ, Ali AH, Lindor KD. Primary biliary cirrhosis. *Annals of Translational Medicine*, 2015; 386(10003):1565-75
40. Cheang WS, Tian XY, Wong WT, Huang Y. The peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors in cardiovascular disease: experimental benefits and clinical challenges. *Br J Pharmacol*. 2015;172(23):5512-5523.
41. Tacke F. Enivivior for the treatment of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis & liver fibrosis. *National Library of Medicine, National Center for Biotechnology Information*; 2018.
42. Xue F, Wei L. THR β agonist for non-alcoholic steatohepatitis treatment: challenges of a

- promising drug. *J Clin Transl Hepatol.* 2024; 12(8):865-872.
43. Bitta P, Paidimari SP, Ayuthu S, Chauhan Y, et.al. Resmetirom: A systematic review of the revolutionizing approach to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis treatment focusing on efficacy, safety, cost-effectiveness, and impact on quality of life. *Cureus.* 2024; 16(9): e69919.
44. Khoo TSWL, Rehman A, Olynyk JK. Tyrosine kinase inhibitors in the treatment of hepatocellular carcinoma. In: National Library of Medicine, Exon Publications; 2019; Chapter 7.
45. Tiffany Sandra Wai Ling Khoo, Arif Rehman, and John K. Olynyk. *Hepatocellular Carcinoma*; 2019; chapter 7.
46. Tovate F, Airoidi C, Sautphale F. Immunotherapy for NAFL disease-related HCC: Lights & Shadows. *World J Gastrointestinal Oncol.* 2022; 14(9):1769-1785
47. Tran Cao H. Histo-typing for liver cancer: What to know about this novel cancer treatment. The University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center. 2025.
48. Tayyeb A, Azam F, Nisar R. Liver Cirrhosis: Update and Current Challenges. 2017; chapter: Regenerative medicine in liver cirrhosis: Promises & pitfalls, DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.68729
49. Yadav P, Singh SK, Rajput S, Allawadhi P, Khurana A, Weis Kirchen R, Navik U. Therapeutic potential of stem cells in regeneration of liver in chronic liver diseases: Current perspectives and future challenges. *Pharmacol Ther.* 2024; 253:108563.
50. Wiest R, Albillos A, Trauner M. Targeting the gut-liver axis in liver disease. *Journal of Hepatology.* 2017; 67(5).
51. Xiaohan X, Wu X, Paullsen KL, Wu L. Targeted therapeutics & novel signaling pathways in NA associated fatty liver/steatohepatitis (NAFL/NASH). *Signal Transduct Target Ther.* 2022; 7(1):287
52. Ilo Chukwu SB, Ugwu Chukwu S, Ukale LO, et al. Advances in drug delivery systems, challenges and future directions. *Heliyon,* 2023;9(6)
53. Jain RK. Delivery of molecular and cellular medicine to solid tumours. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 2001; 46(1-3): 149-168.
54. Chen J, Chen Y, 53. Cheng Y, Gao Y, Zheng J, Li Y, Tong Y, Li Z, Luo W, Zhao C. Liver-targeting drug delivery system by glycyrrhetic acid liposomes modified with glycyrrhetic acid derivative glycyrrhizic. *Oncotarget,* 2017; 8(62):106204-106266.
55. Shrestha H, Bala R, Arora S. Lipid-Based Drug Delivery Systems. *J Pharm (Cairo),* 2014; 2014:801820.
56. Bazinet M, Pantea V, Cebotarescu V, Cojuhari L, Jimbei P, et al. Persistent control of hepatitis B virus and hepatitis delta virus infection following REP 2139-Ca and pegylated interferon therapy in chronic hepatitis B virus/hepatitis delta virus coinfection. *Hepatol Commun.* 2020; 5(2):189-202.
57. Zhou F, Teng F, Deng P, Meng N, Song Z, Feng R. "Recent progress of Nano Drug delivery system for Liver cancer treatment." *Anti-cancer Agents in Medicinal Chemistry,* 2018, 17(14): 1884–1897
58. Warner JB, Guenther SC, Hardesty JE, McClain CJ, Warner DR, Kirpich IA. Liver-specific drug delivery platforms: Applications for the treatment of alcohol-associated liver disease. *World J Gastroenterol,* 2022;28(36):5280-5299.
59. Lanao JM. Frontiers in hepatic drug delivery—grand challenges. *Front Drug Deliv.* 2023; 3:1265446.
60. Gao, F., Feng, X., & Li, X.. Recent advances in polymeric nanoparticles for the treatment of hepatic diseases. *Frontiers in Pharmacology,* 2025; (16). 1528752:1-17.
61. Böttger R, Pauli G, Chao PH, Al Fayed N, Hohenwarter L, Li SD. Lipid-based nanoparticle technologies for liver targeting. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2020; 154-155:79-101.
62. Chu, R., Wang, Y., Kong, J., Pan, T., Yang, Y., & He, J.. Lipid nanoparticles as the drug carrier for targeted therapy of hepatic disorders. *J. Mater. Chem.,* 2024; 12, 4759–4784.
63. Liu B, et al. Drug delivery systems based on mesoporous silica. *Acta Pharm Sin B.* 2025;15(2):809-833.
64. Rana A, Adhikary M, Singh PK, Das BC, Bhatnagar S. "Smart" drug delivery: A window to future of translational medicine. *Front Chem.* 2023; 10:1095598.

65. Gonçalves GAR, Paiva RMA. Gene therapy: advances, challenges and perspectives. *Einstein (São Paulo)*, 2017;15(3):369-375.
66. Prabahar K, Alanazi Z, Qushawy M. Targeted Drug Delivery System: Advantages, Carriers and Strategies. *Indian J Pharm Educ Res.*, 2021;55(2):346-356
67. Yoo J, Park C, Yi G, Lee D, Koo H. Active targeting strategies using biological ligands for nanoparticle drug delivery systems. *Cancers (Basel)*, 2019; 11(5):640.
68. Tian Y, Shi Y. Mechanisms of Targeted Drug Delivery for Liver Cancer: Active, Passive, and Subcellular Strategies. *J Biosci Med.*, 2025; 13(2).
69. Murc S. Challenges in design and characterization of ligand-targeted drug delivery systems. *J Control Release*, 2012; 164(2):125-137.
70. Yan S, Na J, Liu X, Wu P. Different targeting ligands-mediated drug delivery systems for tumour therapy. *Pharmaceutics*, 2024; 16(2):248.

HOW TO CITE: T. Mahesh Kumar*, G. Dhiya, V. Mohana Bharathi, U. Malar Mannan and P. Ananthi, A Systematic Review: Insights on Understanding and Designing Hepatic Drug Delivery Research, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (1), 591-613. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18222767>

